

Influence of Ultrasonic Radiations on the Rheology of some Gel-forming Systems

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Influence of ultrasonic radiations, frequency 1 M c/s, on the plasticity of the gel-forming titanium and zirconium succinate sols has been investigated. The gel-yielding succinate sols exhibit plasticity with a definite yield value. Due to ultrasonic agitation a considerable decrease in the plasticity leading to a significant increase in the gelling time has been observed. The rheological properties of the gel-yielding metal succinate sols are therefore considerably modified by ultrasonic waves.

In an earlier communication¹ we have described the influence of ultrasonic radiations on the pH, conductance, and gelling time of some metal succinate sols. Elsewhere² we have demonstrated the development of an yield value in such sols where it has been pointed out that the gel-yielding succinate sols exhibit structural flow and show plastic behaviour. In a recent publication³, we have investigated the stability of such metal succinate sols.

The influence of ultrasonic waves on the plasticity and yield value of the gel-yielding succinate sols of titanium and zirconium has been studied in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Titanium succinate sols were prepared by adding sodium succinate solution taken short of precipitation to a slight excess of titanium tetrachloride solution. Two samples, (A) and (B), were thus prepared which had the compositions: titanium chloride (containing 11.834 g. of Ti/lit) = 160.0 ml; 0.25 M sodium succinate in sol (A) = 70.0 ml and in sol (B) = 80.0 ml.

The sols were dialysed for purification for a period of 18 hours and were preserved at a cool place to avoid the effects of ageing. The sols set to transparent gels when coagulated with potassium chloride of suitable concentration.

Zirconium succinate sols were prepared by adding sodium succinate solution taken short of precipitation to a slight excess of zirconium nitrate solution. Two samples, (C) and (D), were thus prepared which had the compositions: zirconium nitrate, 0.357 M = 150.0 ml; 0.25 M sodium succinate in sol (C) = 95.0 ml. and in sol (D) = 100.0 ml.

The sols were purified by dialysis for a period of 96 hours. The purified sols set to transparent gels when coagulated with potassium chloride of suitable concentration.

1. *Kolloid Z.*, 1960, 171, 31.

2. Upadhy, Doctoral Thesis, Allahabad University, 1960.

3. *Kolloid Z.*, 1961, 178, 170.

The source of ultrasonic power was a Mullard high frequency generator, type E 7562, with barium titanate crystal having a frequency of 1Mc/sec. and power output of 225 W. The transducer was immersed in a circulation bath maintained at a constant temperature. The sols were placed in a special flat-bottomed ground-stoppered Jens' glass bottles, held vertically above the ultrasonic beam. The distance between the vessel and the transducer was carefully adjusted to effect a good fountain.

Rheological Measurements

The viscosity of the sols at different shearing stresses was obtained by observing the time of flow through a capillary of an Ostwald viscometer corresponding to various pressure differences⁴. The time of flow was determined in both downward (t_1) and upward (t_2) directions. All measurements of the rate of flow were made at a shearing stress where the flow was free from turbulence.

The sols were exposed to ultrasonic waves for different intervals of time (1 hr. and 2 hrs.) and the rheological measurements were made at a bath temperature of $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The results of the investigations are represented graphically in Figs. 1-4.

DISCUSSION

The gel-yielding metal succinate sols investigated, as it appears from Figs. 1 to 4, show anomalous viscosity and exhibit plasticity with a definite yield value. Sols containing coarser particles (B and D) have larger yield values than those containing finer ones (A and C). As a result of exposing the succinate sols to ultrasonic waves, the yield value decreases indicating a depolymerising action (Figs.

FIG. 1. Sol A.

FIG. 2. Sol B.

4. Ghosh and Ayub, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1939, 9, 149.

1 and 2). The gelling time of the exposed sols is therefore, greater than that of the unexposed ones as shown in Tables I and II.

FIG. 3. Sol C.

FIG. 4. Sol D.

TABLE I

Titanium succinate sol (B).

Vol. of sol=2.00 ml. Total vol.=3.0 ml.
Time of exposure=1 hour. Temp.=35°.

N/4-KCl (ml)	0.90	0.80	0.70	0.60	0.50
Gelling time (min.):					
Unexposed	4.00	6.00	9.00	13.50	20.00 mts
Exposed	7.00	10.00	14.50	23.00	31.00 mts

TABLE II

Zirconium succinate sol (D).

Vol. of sol=3.0 ml. Total vol.=5.00 ml.
Time of exposure=1 hour. Temp.=35°.

N/40-KCl(ml)	2.00	1.90	1.80	1.70	1.60 mls
Gelling time (min.):					
Unexposed	6.00	8.00	13.00	16.00	24.00 mts
Exposed.	10.00	12.00	19.00	25.00	36.00 mts

The development of an yield value in these gel-yielding succinate sols is undoubtedly due to the existence of structurations and oriented aggregation in the gelling colloidal succinate systems and it appears that during ultrasonic agitation the depolymerising effects are fairly prominent and the structurations are damaged to such an extent that a significant decrease in the yield value and an equally significant increase in the gelling time are

observed. The ultrasonic effects are chiefly due to cavitation and markedly affect the gel-yielding metal succinate sols investigated in this paper.

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